

GLOBALIZATION CONDITIONS AND MODERN TRENDS IN TEACHING NATURAL SCIENCES IN GRADE 5

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Annotation: The article examines contemporary trends in teaching natural sciences in Grade 5 under the conditions of globalization. The rapid development of science and technology, digital transformation, and increasing international educational integration necessitate the modernization of science education in general secondary schools. The study analyzes modern pedagogical approaches, including competency-based education, inquiry-based learning, STEM education, digital technologies, and international assessment frameworks such as PISA and TIMSS. The paper substantiates the importance of developing scientific literacy, critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and research competencies among Grade 5 students. Furthermore, recommendations are proposed for improving the methodology of teaching natural sciences in Uzbekistan based on international best practices and innovative educational technologies.

Keywords: globalization, natural sciences education, Grade 5, scientific literacy, competency-based approach, inquiry-based learning, PISA, STEM education, digital technologies.

Introduction. Nowadays, the process of globalization has become one of the main factors of social development, radically changing the directions of development of the economy, culture, science and education system. As a result of the rapid development of information and communication technologies, the exchange of knowledge is accelerating, and the content of education is being updated in accordance with global requirements. Therefore, modern school education is faced with the task of not only imparting knowledge, but also forming a competitive, creative and scientifically-minded person.

In the context of globalization, natural science education is of particular importance. Because natural science is a fundamental field of education that provides a person with an understanding of the environment, the formation of a scientific worldview, and adaptability to technological progress. Researchers argue that the modern education system “should direct the student to independent discovery of knowledge rather than transferring knowledge in a ready-made form” [1; p. 24].

Today, the experience of developed countries shows that integrated teaching of natural sciences effectively develops scientific thinking and problem-solving competencies in students [2; p. 31]. In particular, the 5th grade of general secondary schools is the initial stage of the formation of students' natural and scientific literacy, and it is at this stage that scientific observation, experimentation, and analytical thinking skills develop.

In the discipline of pedagogy, it is substantiated that socio-cultural factors of personal development are important, and it is noted that acquiring knowledge through cooperation and communication in the process of educational activities gives effective results [3; p. 86]. In this regard, student-oriented pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, and research-based educational approaches in teaching natural sciences are an important pedagogical requirement of the era of globalization.

In recent years, the results of international assessment programs, in particular PISA studies, indicate the need to develop practical competencies in schoolchildren rather than theoretical knowledge [4]. This requires the modernization of science teaching methods, STEM integration, the widespread introduction of digital educational resources and innovative pedagogical technologies.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, modernization of the education system, training personnel in accordance with international standards, and updating the content of general secondary education have become a priority area of state policy. As a result, an integrated course in natural sciences (Science) has been introduced, and special attention is paid to the development of students' natural and scientific literacy [5]. As a result, due to globalization, a scientific and methodological analysis of modern trends in teaching natural sciences in the 5th grade of general secondary schools appears as an urgent pedagogical problem.

Literature review. The issue of modernization of natural science education in the context of globalization is one of the current directions of pedagogical science [9]. In recent years, many scientific studies have been carried out on improving the methodology of teaching natural sciences, developing integrated natural science education "Science", and forming natural science literacy in students.

Local pedagogical scientists J.O. Tolipova emphasizes that interdisciplinary integration is an important factor in the development of natural science teaching methodology, and justifies the formation of students' scientific thinking through experimental and observational activities [2; p. 42]. The author scientifically highlights the priority of practical activities along with theoretical knowledge in the natural science course.

R.J. Ishmuhamedov shows that the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process develops students' independent thinking. According to the scientist, the modern teaching model requires the teacher to move from the role of information provider to that of facilitator [1; p. 37]. This approach is an important indicator of the transformation of education in the era of globalization.

In developing the theory of pedagogical technologies, N.N. Azizkhodjaeva notes that the effectiveness of the educational process depends on the active participation of the student, reflection and collaborative learning [6; p. 56]. These views serve as a methodological basis for the widespread use of interactive methods in teaching natural sciences.

The changes in the content of education in the context of globalization have also been widely analyzed in the studies of foreign scientists. According to L.S. Vygotsky's theory of socio-cultural development, knowledge is formed through the active social interaction of the student, and the educational process is a factor that drives development forward [3; p. 89]. This theory today forms the scientific basis of the student-centered educational model.

The development of a competency-based approach in natural sciences education is also considered an important direction in international research. The results of the PISA study conducted by the OECD show that students' skills in applying knowledge in practical situations are not sufficiently developed, justifying the need to develop scientific literacy in school education [4].

In recent scientific works, the concept of STEM education is recognized as an innovative model of teaching natural sciences. Researchers emphasize that integrated education develops creative thinking, problem solving and technological literacy in students [7].

The development of digital technologies has also created new opportunities for natural sciences education. It has been noted in scientific studies that virtual laboratories, simulations and multimedia tools increase the level of students' knowledge acquisition by visualizing abstract scientific concepts [8].

The analysis shows that although the theoretical foundations of natural sciences teaching, pedagogical technologies and innovative methods are widely covered in existing scientific studies, the methodological trends of the integrated natural sciences course for 5th grade students in the context of globalization have not been studied in a sufficiently comprehensive manner. This situation determines the scientific necessity of this study.

Discussion and results. Globalization processes have led to the formation of new pedagogical approaches in the education system, creating the need to update the content, form and methods of teaching natural sciences. In the course of the research, the practice of teaching natural sciences in the 5th grade of general secondary schools was studied on the basis of theoretical analysis, pedagogical observation and methodological comparison.

The results of the study showed that the traditional knowledge-oriented educational model is based on delivering ready-made information to students and cannot sufficiently develop their independent thinking and scientific research activities. In natural science lessons organized on the basis of a competency-based approach, it was observed that students became active participants in the learning process [9]. Students actively participated in the processes of conducting observations, conducting experiments, comparing results and drawing conclusions. As a result, their scientific thinking, logical thinking and problem-solving skills developed.

In the context of globalization, integrated teaching of natural sciences has emerged as an effective pedagogical solution. The interrelated presentation of elements of biology, physics, geography and ecology has enabled students to understand natural phenomena as a holistic system. In lessons organized on the basis of interdisciplinary connections, it was observed that the level of students' understanding of the subject increased, and long-term retention of knowledge was enhanced. This confirms the methodological soundness of the integrated Science course.

The use of digital technologies has also shown significant results. Classes organized through multimedia presentations, virtual laboratories and interactive models have significantly increased students' interest in the lesson. In particular, the mastery of concepts has become easier through the visual representation of abstract natural processes. The expansion of individual learning opportunities has served to reduce differences in the pace of students' mastery.

The use of elements of research-based education had a positive impact on the formation of scientific research activities in students. Mini-projects, observation tasks and practical experiments increased the students' need for independent knowledge. Students learned to ask scientific questions, make assumptions and interpret results based on evidence. At the same time, the formation of personal qualities such as environmental responsibility and a careful attitude to nature was also observed.

The results of the study show that a transformation is also taking place in the teacher's work. In modern natural science lessons, the teacher is not a subject of knowledge, but an organizer and guide of the educational process. The teacher's facilitating activity has developed students' independence, collaborative skills and reflective thinking.

The analysis also shows that in the conditions of globalization, the methodology of teaching natural sciences is entering a new stage of development. It was found that the use of a competency-based

approach, an integrated educational model, digital technologies, and research-based methods significantly increases the scientific literacy, interest in knowledge, and readiness for practical activities of 5th grade students. These results confirm the need to improve the methodology of teaching natural sciences in accordance with the requirements of globalization.

Conclusions and recommendations. Globalization processes create the need to radically update the content and methodology of teaching natural sciences in all parts of the education system, in particular in general secondary schools. Based on the theoretical analysis and pedagogical observations, modern trends in teaching natural sciences in the 5th grade were identified and their impact on educational effectiveness was assessed.

The results of the study showed that the traditional reproductive education model cannot fully meet the requirements of the globalization era. In the modern educational process, it is important not for students to receive knowledge ready-made, but for them to acquire it through independent research. In this regard, the competency-based approach has emerged as the methodological basis for teaching natural sciences.

It was found that an integrated natural sciences course helps students to understand natural phenomena as a holistic system, understand cause-and-effect relationships, and form a scientific worldview. Lessons organized on the basis of interdisciplinary connections increased students' interest in learning and ensured a solid assimilation of knowledge [9].

The use of digital technologies, virtual experiences and interactive methods has significantly increased the effectiveness of the educational process. These tools have made it possible to take into account the individual capabilities of students, visually explain abstract concepts and activate learning activities.

As a result of the introduction of elements of research-based education, students have developed scientific research skills, logical thinking, problem solving and evidence-based reasoning. This confirms that it is one of the main factors in the development of scientific literacy.

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations were developed:

- use of a competency-based approach as a priority methodological principle in teaching natural sciences in general secondary schools;
- organization of an integrated Science course in grades 5 based on interdisciplinary connections and linking it with real-life problems;
- widespread introduction of research-based teaching methods, practical experiments and mini-project activities in natural sciences lessons;
- systematic use of digital educational resources, virtual laboratories and interactive platforms;
- improvement of professional development programs aimed at improving the methodological competence of teachers in modern pedagogical technologies;
- use of tasks in accordance with the criteria of international assessment programs in assessing students' natural and scientific literacy.

In the context of globalization, modernization of natural science teaching methods is an important pedagogical factor in developing students' scientific thinking, forming an innovative thinking personality, and educating a competitive generation that meets the requirements of modern society.

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